

Name: Joshua Wilbur

Language/LID: Sm'algyax (Coast Tsimshian) / 522

Date Completed: 14th February 2004

Sources:

1. Stebbins, Tonya. *On the status of intermediate form classes: Words, clitics, and affixes in Sm'algyax (Coast Tsimshian)*. in *Linguistic Typology* 7, 2003. p. 383-415. Note: all information and pages from this source unless stated otherwise.
2. Stebbins, Tonya. *Fighting Language Endangerment: Community Directed Research on Sm'algyax (Coast Tsimshian)*. Kyoto: Nakanish Printing Co., Ltd., 2003.
3. Dunn, John Aser. *A Referenece Grammar for the Coast Tsimshian Language*. Ottawa: National Museum of Canada, 1979.
4. Dunn, John Aser. *A Practical Dictionary of the Coast Tsimshian Language*. Ottawa: National Museum of Canada, 1978
5. Mulder, Jean Gail. *Ergativity in Coast Tsimshian (Sm'algyax)*. Berkley: UC Press, 1994.

basic facts (p. 385):

-Sm'algyax has clitics* with differing degrees of phonological dependency (prosodic and phonological)

*note: "...the term clitic is used here to identify forms positively that show phrase level dependency from a grammatical perspective in addition to some degree of phonological dependency." (p. 385)

-adverbs and verbs are phonological words carrying stress

-clause-initial clitics form a separate P- ω without stress

-"word" means "a form that may stand alone as a phonological and grammatical word. In addition, these forms may host a number of clitics and affixes" (p. 389)

form class inventory (note: both lexical and grammatical classes include words, clitics, and affixes) (sec. 2):

-lexical words: verbs, nouns, adverbs, quantifiers, numerals

-grammatical words: demonstratives, independent pronouns, prepositions, nominal conjunctions, interjections, interrogatives

-clause-initial clitics (unstressed, lean prosodically on following lexical word): clausal negatives, TAM, clausal conjunctions, subordinators, ergative dependent pronouns, several discourse markers

-NP-initial clitics (occur on boundary of NP, phonologically dependant on a neighboring form): possessive marker, dependency markers

-lexical clitics (proclitics): modifiers, locatives

-affixes: derivational prefixes, absolutive dependent pronouns, aspectual suffixes, number marking morphology, indefinite markers, evidential -*gat*

Stress rules (p. 400):

-typically falls on ultima

-primary stress is a feature of lexical words only

-only noun and verb stems take primary stress marking (p. 406)

more stress rules (in 3 p. 5-9):

-normally ultimate σ

-but, if the final σ is a suffix or connective, then stress is on the penultimate

-an epenthetic vowel (either a, i, or ɨ) due to a "complex consonant cluster"* at a word boundary is unstressed

*Dunn doesn't define what exactly a complex consonant cluster is, but based on the data from him and Mulder it is a consonant cluster across a morpheme boundary; Mulder says (in 5 p. 24) that "an epenthetic vowel is sometimes inserted when a complex consonant cluster is created at the end of a word by the addition of one or more suffixes. This vowel is a short unstressed vowel that varies from [ɨ] to [ʌ] depending on its environment." and she gives these examples:

waay 'find' + 'nu '1sg.O' → [wai-t'nu] 'find me'

'niidz 'see' + 'nu '1sg.O' → ['ni-ʒʌ'nu] 'see me'

-short vowels are often lengthened when stressed

Pausing rule (p. 401):

-after adverb, verb, noun (including inflectional suffixes), and after clause-initial clitics

Why clause-initial clitics are and yet aren't P- ω (p. 399-402):

-prosodically dependent on following lexical word (ie: can't carry primary stress)

-pausing possible after clause-initial clitics

-potentially morphologically complex (can take ergative series of dependent pronouns)

-may occur alone or in various combinations

syllable rules (p. 403 in 1 and from analysis of dictionary entries in 4):

-minimal restraint on σ : CVV (where VV is either a diphthong or a long V)

How the P- ω of NP-initial clitics (possessive and dependency markers) don't align with their G- ω (p. 404-7):

-phonologically dependent on a nearby word, but grammatically dependent on an entire phrase

-always at the beginning of the NP regardless of the actual phonological host

-the possessive marker is always at beginning of the NP and is phonologically a prefix to the first word in the NP (p. 404)

-the dependency markers are always syntactically dependent on the following NP, but phonologically on whatever precedes them (they can cause stem-final lenition and vowel epenthesis) (p. 405-7)

-examples:

possessive marker

Ea asdisgüüyu nadzem ludat'oom hoonu
ta asdi=sgüü=u na=dzem ludat'oom hoon-u
IMPF aside=cut-1A POSS=boiled canned.fish-1POSS
'I put my boiled canned fish aside.'

dependency marker (P- ω marked by spaces, G- ω marked by brackets)

Luk'wil aam wila ganuutg[a k'abatgüüt+k] ta Ha'libilbaalax
luk'wil aam wila ga-nuutg[=a k'abatgüüt+k] ta Ha'libilbaalax
really good MF PL-dress.up[=DM children] IMPF Halloween
'The children are dressed up really nice for Halloween'

-or another example from Stebbins (in 2 p. 83):

Niidz[as Nadine][t Isabelle]
niits[=s Nadine][=t Isabelle]
see[=DM.A Nadine][=DM.O Isabelle]
'Nadine saw Isabelle'

modifiers and locatives (p. 408-9):

-phonologically dependent on the presence of a noun and/or a verb because they cannot occur without a noun and/or verb, but bound to a specific slot in the phrase.

example (p. 410):

Nüdzu wilt dibaada duus[a tğudzagm wüts'iin]
niits-u wilt di-baa-t=a duus[=a tgu=dzak=m wüts'iin]
see-1A SUBORD with-run-3O=DM cat=DM little=dead=DM mouse
'I saw a cat running with a dead mouse'

only 2 morphophonological processes in Sm'algyax (in 2 p. 109):

-Vowel harmony: the V in a derivational prefix is "influenced by the first sound in the following syllable" (no examples given)

-stem-final lenition, which sometimes occurs with affixation:

voiceless obstruent \rightarrow voiced / $_{-}+K_{[voiced]}$

-And also in fast speech only (in 2 p. 228):

k' \rightarrow [g ~ G] / # $_{-}$

phonological rules relevant at word boundaries (in 3 p. 11, 12):

- /q/ → [q ~ x] / _#
- /ʔ/ → [ʔ ~ h] / #_

reduplication (typical for plural forms) (in 3, multiple pages starting at p. 13):

- based on reduplicating part of the first syllable or first strong syllable only
- for example, most typical version (class 1 plural reduplication = copy first C, add a vowel and palatal plosive):

$C_1 \dots [sg] \rightarrow C_1 V K C_1 \dots [pl]$

duus → dikduus 'cat/cats'

dziiu → dzikdziiu 'dolphin/dolphins'